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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MIGLITOL
BIOADHESIVE MICROSPHERES USING DIFFERENT
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Abstract:

This study investigates the formulation and characterization of Miglitol microspheres using various polymers, including sodium alginate with carbopol 934, carbopol 971, and HPMC K4M. UV spectroscopic analysis confirmed Miglitol's λ_{max} at 269 nm, with a high correlation coefficient (0.998) for its calibration curve. FTIR spectroscopy indicated no significant chemical interactions between Miglitol and the polymers. Microsphere yield, drug entrapment efficiency, particle size, swelling ratio, mucoadhesion, and drug release were systematically evaluated. Results showed that higher polymer concentrations generally enhanced yield, drug entrapment efficiency, and swelling ratios. Dissolution studies demonstrated sustained release of Miglitol, with the Korsmeyer-Peppas model best describing the release kinetics. This comprehensive characterization highlights the potential of these polymer combinations for controlled drug delivery systems.

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INTRODUCTION:

The oral route is the most popular and cost-effective method for drug delivery, favored for its convenience and naturalness. Despite its popularity, traditional oral drug delivery often necessitates frequent dosing, leading to fluctuating drug levels and potential side effects. Controlled release systems, designed to maintain steady drug levels over extended periods, address these issues by providing more consistent therapeutic effects and reducing side effects. Microspheres, which are small spherical particles made from biodegradable polymers or natural substances, enhance drug delivery by offering controlled, sustained, or targeted release. They are advantageous for applications such as taste masking, drug protection, and sustained release. However, challenges like short residence times and poor in vivo correlation persist. To overcome these, bioadhesive microspheres have been developed to improve drug absorption and extend residence time in the gastrointestinal tract, thereby enhancing bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy.

Mucoadhesive drug delivery systems utilize the property of bioadhesion, where polymers adhere to mucosal surfaces, enhancing drug localization and prolonging residence time at the target site. Bioadhesion encompasses three types: adhesion between biological phases, adhesion of biological phases to artificial substrates, and adhesion of artificial materials to biological substrates. Mucoadhesive systems, which involve adhesion to mucus surfaces, offer advantages such as improved drug bioavailability, enhanced tissue contact, and extended drug release. Mechanisms of mucoadhesion include electronic, wetting, adsorption, diffusion, mechanical, and cohesive theories. Polymers used in mucoadhesive systems include hydrophilic polymers (e.g., poly(acrylic acid), chitosan), hydrogels, thiolated polymers, and lectin-based polymers, each offering unique adhesion properties. Methods for preparing mucoadhesive microspheres include air suspension, coacervation, spray drying, solvent evaporation, polymerization, and wet inversion, each providing different approaches to achieving effective drug delivery and prolonged action.

Table 1: LIST OF MATERIALS

List of Chemicals	Manufacturing Company
Miglitol HCl	msn labs
Sodium alginate	Sisco
Carbopol 934	Sisco
Carbopol 971	Sisco
HPMC K 4 M	Sisco
Calcium chloride dehydrate	Sisco
Methanol	Merk
Hydrochloric acid	Merk

METHODOLOGY:**Preformulation Studies and Method of Preparation:**

Spectroscopic Studies: For spectral analysis, a 0.1N HCl solution (pH 1.2) was prepared by diluting 8 ml of HCl in 1000 ml of distilled water. Miglitol's λ_{max} was determined by preparing a 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution in 0.1N HCl and scanning it between 200-400 nm, revealing a λ_{max} of 269 nm. A standard calibration curve for Miglitol was created by preparing a stock solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in methanol, diluting it to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and further diluting to 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in 0.1N HCl. Absorbance at 269 nm was measured, resulting in a calibration curve with a correlation coefficient of 0.998, a slope of 0.028, and an intercept of 0.004.

Compatibility Studies: Compatibility between Miglitol and excipients was assessed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The FTIR spectra of Miglitol, polymers, and formulations were compared to ensure drug-excipient compatibility, using the KBr pellet method on a Shimadzu FTIR 8400 spectrophotometer.

Method of Preparation: Microspheres were prepared via ionotropic gelation. Sodium alginate and a mucoadhesive polymer were mixed with Miglitol in purified water to create a viscous dispersion. This mixture was then added dropwise into a 4% calcium chloride solution with stirring at 200 rpm. After 30 minutes, the microspheres were collected, washed with water to remove excess calcium, and air-dried.

Figure 1: Photograph of prepared microspheres

Table 2: Prepared formulation of Bioadhesive Microspheres

S.No.	FORMULATION CODE	DRUG:POLYMER RATIO	POLYMER RATIO
1	T ₁	1:2.5	Na alginate :Carbopol 934 (1.5:0.5)
2	T ₂	1:3	Na alginate:Carbopol 934 (2:1)
3	T ₃	1:3.5	Na alginate:Carbopol 934 (2.5:1)
4	T ₄	1:4	Na alginate:Carbopol 934 (3:1)
5	T ₅	1:2.5	Na alginate:Carbopol 971 (1.5:0.5)
6	T ₆	1:3	Na alginate:Carbopol 971 (2:1)
7	T ₇	1:3.5	Na alginate:Carbopol 971 (2.5:1)
8	T ₈	1:4	Na alginate:Carbopol 971 (3:1)
9	T ₉	1:2.5	Na alginate:HPMC K 4M (1.5:0.5)
10	T ₁₀	1:3	Na alginate:HPMC K 4M (2:1)
11	T ₁₁	1:3.5	Na alginate:HPMC K 4M (2.5:1)
12	T ₁₂	1:4	Na alginate:HPMC K 4M (3:1)

Characterization of microspheres:

Microsphere Evaluation:

Percentage Yield: The yield was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage Yield} = \frac{\text{Practical Mass of Microspheres}}{\text{Theoretical Mass of Polymer + Drug}} * 100$$

Drug Entrapment Efficiency: To assess drug entrapment, microspheres equivalent to 15 mg of Miglitol were crushed and dissolved in methanol and simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2). After 24 hours, the solution was filtered, and absorbance was measured at 269 nm. The entrapment efficiency was calculated as:

Drug Entrapment Efficiency=
Experimental Drug Content/
Theoretical Drug Content $\times 100\%$

Particle Size Analysis: Particle size was determined using an optical microscope calibrated such that 1 eyepiece micrometer unit equaled 12.5 μm . The average particle size was calculated using Edmondson's equation:

$$D_{\text{mean}} = \sum d / n$$

Swelling Study: Swelling ratio of microspheres was measured gravimetrically in simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2). The swelling ratio (%) was calculated by:

$$\text{Swelling Ratio} = (W_t - W_0) / W_0 \times 100$$

where, W_0 is the initial weight and W_t is the final weight of the microspheres.

Mucoadhesive Property: The mucoadhesion was assessed using the wash-off method with goat stomach mucosa. Microspheres adhered to mucosal surfaces were counted after immersion in simulated

gastric fluid (pH 1.2) at 37°C. The percentage mucoadhesion was calculated as:

Mucoadhesion (%) =

$$\frac{\text{Number of Microspheres Adhered}}{\text{Number of Microspheres Applied}} \times 100$$

In Vitro Drug Release Study: Drug release was measured using the USP type-I rotating basket method in simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2) at 37°C and 50 rpm. Aliquots were analyzed at set intervals for drug release at 269 nm. Fresh fluid was added to maintain sink conditions.

In Vitro Drug Release Kinetics: The release data were fitted into the Korsmeyer-Peppas equation:

$$M_t / M_{\infty} = K t^n$$

where M_t / M_{∞} is the fractional drug release, t is time, K is the release rate constant, and n is the diffusional exponent, indicating the release mechanism.

Table 3

Release exponent (n)	Drug transport mechanism	Rate as a function of time
0.5	Fickian diffusion	$t^{-0.5}$
$0.5 < n < 1.0$	Anomalous transport or non-Fickian	t^{n-1}
1.0	Case-II transport	Zero-order release
Higher than 1.0	Super transport	Cas t^{n-1}

Fickian vs. Non-Fickian Diffusion:

If $n < 0.5$: Drug release follows Fickian diffusion (molecular transport unaffected by polymer relaxation).

If $n > 0.5$: Drug release is non-Fickian and controlled by polymer relaxation.

Release Kinetics Models:

Zero Order: % R = kt

Ideal for prolonged release (e.g., transdermal systems, osmotic systems, matrix tablets with low soluble drugs).

First Order: $\log(\text{fraction unreleased}) = kt / 2.303$
Used for hydrolysis kinetics and release profiles of water-soluble drugs in porous matrices.

Higuchi Matrix: % R = $kt^{0.5}$

Applicable to drugs in uniform swellable polymer matrices (e.g., matrix tablets with water-soluble drugs).

- Peppas-Korsmeyer Equation: $\% R = kt^n$, $\log \% R = \log k + n \log t$

- Useful when the release mechanism is known or involves multiple phenomena; n characterizes the release mechanism.

Table 4

Value of	n	Mechanism
0.5		Fickian Diffusion (Higuchi Matrix)
$0.5 < n < 1$		Anomalous Transport
1		Case – II transport (Zero Order Release)
$n > 1$		Super Case Transport

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preformulation Studies

Spectroscopic Studies

Determination of λ_{max} : A 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution of Miglitol was scanned between 200 and 400 nm. The drug showed a maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at 269 nm in simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2). The correlation between concentration and absorbance was approximately 0.998, with a slope of 0.028 and an intercept of 0.004, indicating good reproducibility.

Figure 2: UV Spectrum of Miglitol in simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2)

Calibration curve of Miglitol in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2

Table 6.1 shows the calibration curve data of Miglitol in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2 at 269nm. Fig. 6.2 shows the standard calibration curve with a regression value of 0.998, slope of 0.028 and intercept of 0.004 in simulated gastric fluid pH(1.2). The curve was found to be linear in the concentration range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Table 5: Calibration curve data for Miglitol in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2

CONCENTRATION ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	ABSORBANCE
2	0.051
4	0.110
6	0.163
8	0.221
10	0.290

Figure 3: Standard graph Of Miglitol in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2

Compatibility studies:

Drug-Polymer Compatibility Studies

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to assess potential interactions between Miglitol and the polymers used in the formulation. FTIR spectra of the formulations were compared with

those of pure Miglitol. The results showed that the characteristic absorption peaks of pure Miglitol were present in the formulated microspheres with no significant shift, indicating no chemical interaction between Miglitol and the polymers.

Figure 4: FT-IR spectra of Miglitol

Figure 5: FT-IR spectra of Miglitol +Sodium alginate

Figure 6: FT-IR spectra of Miglitol +Carbopol 934

Figure 7: FT-IR spectra of OPTIMIZED FORMULATION

Evaluation and characterisation of microspheres:**Percentage yield:****Product Yield Analysis**

As the polymer ratio in the formulation increased, the product yield also improved. Lower yields in some cases were attributed to issues such as needle blockages, drug-polymer solution wastage, polymer solution adhesion to magnetic beads, and loss of microspheres during washing. The percentage yield varied as follows:

- Sodium alginate with carbopol 934: 80% to 88%
- Sodium alginate with carbopol 971: 62.22% to 87%
- Sodium alginate with HPMC K4M: 80% to 87.5%

Detailed yield percentages are shown in Table 6.3 and Figures 6.7 to 6.9.

Drug entrapment efficiency:

The percentage drug entrapment efficiency of Miglitol varied as follows:

- Sodium alginate with carbopol 934: 82.66% to 88.66%
- Sodium alginate with carbopol 971: 53.2% to 76.66%
- Sodium alginate with HPMC K4M: 66.73% to 79.2%

Entrapment efficiency increased with higher polymer concentrations. Increased polymer concentration raises the viscosity of the dispersed phase, which in turn increases particle size and reduces drug diffusion into the external phase, leading to higher entrapment efficiency. The detailed values are shown in Table 6.3 and Figures 6.7 to 6.9.

Table 6: Percentage yield and percentage drug entrapment efficiency of the prepared microspheres

S.No.	Formulation code	% yield	Drug Content (mg)	% Drug entrapment efficiency
1	T ₁	80	12.40	82.66±1.16
2	T ₂	83.33	12.66	84.4±1.08
3	T ₃	85	12.70	84.66±1.27
4	T ₄	88	13.29	88.66±0.90
5	T ₅	62.22	8.07	53.2±0.67
6	T ₆	80	8.25	55±0.56
7	T ₇	80	10.33	68.86±0.83
8	T ₈	87	11.5	76.66±1.67
9	T ₉	80	10.01	66.73±1.19
10	T10	86	10.5	70±0.96
11	T11	86.66	11.25	75±0.95
12	T12	87.5	11.88	79.2±0.88

Figure 8: Comparison of % Yield and % drug entrapment efficiency microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 934 as copolymer

Figure 9: Comparison of % Yield and % drug entrapment efficiency microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 971 as copolymer

Figure 10 : Comparison of % Yield and % drug entrapment efficiency microspheres containing sodium alginate along with HPMC K 4 M as copolymer

Particle size analysis:

The mean size increased with increasing polymer concentration which is due to a significant increase in the viscosity, thus leading to an increased droplet size and finally a higher microspheres size. Microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 934 as copolymer had a size range of 512 μ m to 826 μ m, microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 971 as copolymer exhibited a size range

between 517 μ m to 834 μ m and microspheres containing sodium alginate along with HPMC K 4 M as copolymer had a size range of 664 μ m to 903 μ m. The particle size data is presented in Tables 6.4 to 6.15 and displayed in Figure 6.10 to 6.12. The effect of drug to polymer ratio on particle size is displayed in Figure 6.13 . The particle size as well as % drug entrapment efficiency of the microspheres increased with increase in the polymer concentration.

Table 7: Particle size data of T₁

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
200-300	250	9		
300-400	350	13		512±1.52μm
400-500	450	17		
500-600		29		
		2250		
		4550		
		7650		
	550			
600-700		15950		
		20800		
		Σnd=51200	650	
			32	
			Σn=100	

Table 8: Particle size data of T₂

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE (d)	RANGE	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
300-400	350		15		
400-500	450		13		617±1.16μm
500-600	550		18		
600-700	650		12		
700-800	750		28	21000	
800-900	850		14	11900	
			Σn=100	Σnd=61700	

Table 9: Particle size data of T₃

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
400-500	450	10		
500-600	550	12		711±0.56μm
600-700	650	18		
700-800	750	27		
800-900		20250	33	
		28050	Σn=100	
		Σnd=		

Table 10: Particle size data of T₄

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (µm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (µm)
500-600	550	6		826±0.58µm
600-700 700-800	650 750	12 16		
800-900	850	32	27200	
900-1000	950	34	32300	
		∑n=100	∑nd=82600	

Figure 11: Average particle size of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 934 as copolymer

Table 11: Particle size data of T₅

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
200-300	250	8		
300-400		12		517±1.16μm
400-500		18		
	350 450			
500-600	550	29	15950	
600-700	650	33	21450	
		∑n=100	∑nd=51700	

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
400-500	450	6		
500-600		8		792±1.17μm
600-700		19		
700-800				
	550 650 750			
800-900	850	26	22100	
900-1000	950	31	29450	
		∑n=100	∑nd=79200	

Table 12: Particle size data of T₆

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (µm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	n	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (µm)
300-400	350	12		
400-500 500-600		4	11	642±0.59 µm
		4		
	450 550	8		
600-700	650	14		
700-800		9100	31	
		23250		
		14450		
		$\sum nd=64200$ 750		
800-900	850	17	$\sum n=100$	

Table 13: Particle size data of T₈

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (µm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (µm)
500-600	550	6	3300	834±0.59µm
600-700	650	11	7150	
700-800	750	13	9750	
800-900	850	33	28050	
900-1000	950	37	35150	
		∑n=100	∑nd=83400	

Figure 12: Average particle size of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 971 as copolymer**Table 14: Particle size data of T₉**

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (µm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (µm)
400-500	450	18		

500-600		8	19		664±0.59 μm
600-700			18		
700-800		1	21		
		1			
		1			
	550 650 750				
800-900	20400		24	Σn=100	
	Σnd=66400	850			

Table 15: Particle size data of T₁₀

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
400-500	450	8		

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (μm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	nd	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (μm)
500-600		12		774±0.60 μm
600-700		10		
700-800		17		
	550 650 750			
800-900	850	24	20400	
900-1000	950	29	27550	
		Σn=100	Σnd=77400	

600-700	650	2		
700-800 800-900		3		903±0.60µm
		35		
	750 850			
900-1000	950	60	57000	
		$\sum n=100$	$\sum nd=90300$	

Table 16: Particle size data of T₁₁

PARTICLE SIZE RANGE (µm)	MIDPOINT SIZE RANGE (d)	FREQUENCY (n)	n	AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE (µm)
500-600	550	8		
600-700 700-800		4	14	814±0.59µm
		9	17	
	650 750	1		
800-900	850	28		
900-1000	23800	33 $\sum n=100$		
	31350			
	$\sum nd=81400$ 950			

Table 6.15: Particle size data of T₁₂

Figure 13: Average particle size of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with HPMC K 4 M as copolymer

Figure 14: Comparison of average particle size of prepared microspheres

Swelling Ratio Analysis

The swelling ratio, which reflects the percentage of water absorbed by the hydrogel, is crucial for mucoadhesion and drug release in polymeric drug delivery systems. Swellability data, shown in Table 6.16, indicate that an increase in polymer concentration enhances the swelling ratio. Specifically:

- Sodium alginate with carbopol 934: Swelling increased from 28% to 85%.
- Sodium alginate with carbopol 971: Swelling increased from 24% to 64%.
- Sodium alginate with HPMC K4M: Swelling increased from 31% to 85%.

These results demonstrate that the polymer concentration directly influences the swelling ratio, affecting drug availability and diffusion. Swelling percentages are illustrated in Figures 6.16 to 6.18, and the impact of the drug-to-polymer ratio on swelling is shown in Figure 6.19.

Table 17: Percentage swelling of the prepared microspheres

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	INITIAL (Wt)	FINAL (Wt)	PERCENTAGE SWELLING
1	T ₁	10	12.8	28±0.60
2	T ₂	10	14.2	42±0.59
3	T ₃	10	16.2	62±0.58
4	T ₄	10	18.5	85±0.59
5	T ₅	10	12.4	24±0.62
6	T ₆	10	13.9	39±0.59
7	T ₇	10	15.5	55±0.56
8	T ₈	10	16.4	64±0.59
9	T ₉	10	13.1	31±0.60
10	T10	10	15.3	53±0.59
11	T11	10	16.7	67±0.58
12	T12	10	18.5	85±0.59

Figure 15: Percentage swelling of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 934 as copolymer

Figure 16: Percentage swelling of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 971 as copolymer

Figure 17: Percentage swelling of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with HPMC K 4 M as copolymer

Figure 18: Comparison of percentage swelling of prepared microspheres

In-vitro mucoadhesion test:

As the polymer to drug ratio increased, microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 934 as copolymer exhibited % mucoadhesion ranging from 65 to 85%, microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 971 as copolymer exhibited % mucoadhesion ranging from 60 to 75% and microspheres containing sodium alginate along with HPMC K4M as copolymer exhibited % mucoadhesion ranging from 60 to 80%.

The rank of order of mucoadhesion is carbopol 934 > HPMC K 4 M > carbopol 971. The results of in-vitro mucoadhesion test are compiled in Table 6.17. Effect of polymer proportion on % mucoadhesion is depicted in Fig. 6.20 to 6.22 and comparative depiction of % mucoadhesion is depicted in Fig. 6.23.

Table 18: Percentage mucoadhesion of the prepared microspheres

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	No. OF MICROSPHERES		PERCENTAGE MUCOADHESION
		INITIAL	FINAL	
1	T ₁	20	13	65±0.59
2	T ₂	20	14	70±0.60
3	T ₃	20	15	75±0.59
4	T ₄	20	17	85±0.60
5	T ₅	20	12	60±1.52
6	T ₆	20	13	65±1.53
7	T ₇	20	14	70±0.99

8	T ₈	20	15	75±0.95
9	T ₉	20	12	60±0.98
10	T10	20	14	70±0.96
11	T11	20	15	75±1.52
12	T12	20	16	80±1.03

Figure 19: Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 934 as copolymer

Figure 20: Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with carbopol 971 as copolymer

Figure 21: Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing sodium alginate along with HPMC K 4 M as copolymer

Figure 22: Comparison of percentage mucoadhesion of prepared microspheres

In-vitro drug release studies:

Dissolution Studies:

Dissolution studies were conducted using USP type I apparatus with pH 1.2 media. The results are summarized in Tables 6.18 to 6.20, and cumulative percentage drug release versus time plots are shown in Figures 6.24 (formulations T1 to T4), 6.25 (T5 to T8), and 6.26 (T9 to T12). Korsmeyer-Peppas plots for all formulations are displayed in Figures 6.27 to 6.30.

- **Formulations T1-T4** (Sodium alginate with Carbopol 934): Maximum release ranged from 90.6% to 94.66% over 9 to 12 hours.
- **Formulations T5-T8** (Sodium alginate with Carbopol 971): Maximum release ranged from 89.55% to 92.22% over 9 to 12 hours.
- **Formulations T9-T12** (Sodium alginate with HPMC K4M): Maximum release ranged from 90% to 92.6% over 9 to 12 hours.

Increased polymer concentration led to more sustained release, with higher polymer-to-drug ratios resulting in decreased drug release. This is due to the increased density of the polymer matrix, which lengthens the diffusion path and reduces the effective surface area for drug release, controlled by swelling and diffusion mechanisms.

Table 19: carbopol 934

TIME (h)	CUMULATIVE PRECENT OF DRUG RELEASED			
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
0	0	0	0	0
1	24.88 ±0.55	21.11±0.47	18.66±0.66	15.88±0.57
2	31.55±1.02	31.55±0.57	25.11±1.12	24.22±0.87
3	42.44±1.15	39.77±0.50	35.44±0.71	32.66±0.76
4	53.55± 0.86	47.77±0.72	40.66±0.72	39.33±0.75
5	62±1.14	56.66±0.55	52±1.03	47.55±0.74
6	74.66±0.73	62.44±0.65	57.33±0.73	55.77±0.57
7	83.55±0.06	69.55±0.42	63.11±0.62	61.77±0.56
8	89.33±0.65	75.33±0.67	69.11±0.81	69.55±0.54
9	92.66±0.69	84.66±0.48	75.33±0.65	77.55±0.45
10	85.55±0.69	90.66±0.90	82.66±0.67	85.55±0.57
11	80.22±0.61	84.22±0.57	90.66±0.78	90.66±0.68
12	78.88±0.78	80.88±0.34	89.55±0.61	94.66±0.74

Figure 23: carbopol 934

Table 20: carbopol 971

TIME (h)	CUMULATIVE PRECENT OF DRUG RELEASED			
	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇	T ₈
0	0	0	0	0
1	27.77±0.51	22.44±0.75	18.44±0.82	17.11±0.75
2	36.44±0.77	32.22±0.86	29.33±0.83	26.44±0.97
3	43.77±0.91	40.88±0.89	39.55±0.76	37.55±0.53
4	54.66±0.45	48.66±0.56	45.55±0.90	46.88±0.52
5	64.01±0.69	57.55±0.51	57.33±0.82	55.77±0.85
6	75.77±0.68	63.55±0.55	65.33±0.98	63.55±0.84
7	84.65±0.87	70.44±1.13	71.55±0.68	71.33±0.98
8	90±0.78	76.55±0.75	77.56±0.75	75.77±0.58
9	92.22±0.80	85.55±0.61	81.55±0.74	79.77±0.59
10	84.88±0.67	91.33±0.92	83.33±0.87	82.44±0.73
11	79.55±0.67	85.77±0.60	89.55±0.87	86.88±0.81
12	77.55±0.62	81.11±0.94	87.55±0.80	90.66±0.89

Figure24: carbopol 971

Table 21: HPMC K 4 M

TIME (h)	CUMULATIVE PRECENT OF DRUG RELEASED			
	T ₉	T ₁₀	T ₁₁	T ₁₂
0	0	0	0	0
1	25.77±0.80	21.55±0.94	18.66±0.68	16.44±0.91
2	35.33±0.96	31.77±0.68	26.55±0.84	27.11±0.96
3	43.55±0.90	40.44±0.75	36.55±0.90	36.44±0.67
4	54±0.88	48.44±0.72	43.66±0.73	45.55±0.59
5	63.55±0.82	57.11±0.98	54.55±0.80	55.33±0.92
6	75.33±0.78	63.11±1.15	62.33±0.94	63.11±1.03
7	84±0.98	70.22±0.55	67.68±0.48	71.55±0.70
8	89.77±0.59	76±0.96	73.55±0.70	76.44±1.19
9	92.66±0.61	85.11±0.99	78.55±0.60	80.66±0.59
10	85.11±0.93	91.33±0.91	83±0.91	85.55±0.65
11	80.66±1.09	85.33±0.86	90±0.92	89.55±0.85
12	78±1.12	81.11±0.99	87.55±0.68	92.44±0.89

Figure 25:HPMC K 4 M

Figure 26: Korsmeyer-Peppas plots of Miglitol microspheres formulations T₁, T₂ and T₃

Figure 27: Korsmeyer-Peppas plots of Miglitol microspheres formulations T4, T5 and T6

Figure 28: Korsmeyer-Peppas plots of Miglitol microspheres formulations T7, T8 and T9

Figure 29: Korsmeyer-Peppas plots of Miglitol microspheres formulations T₁₀, T₁₁, T₁₂

In-vitro drug release kinetics:

For understanding the mechanism of drug release and release rate kinetics of the drug from dosage form, the in-vitro drug dissolution data obtained was fitted to various mathematical models such as zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix, and Krosmeyer-Peppas model. The values are compiled in Table 6.21. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was used as an indicator of the best fitting for each of the models considered. The kinetic data analysis of all the

formulations reached higher coefficient of determination with the Korsmeyer Peppas model ($R^2 = 0.914$ to 0.996) whereas release exponent value (n) ranged from 0.498 to 0.743 . From the coefficient of determination and release exponent values, it can be suggested that the mechanism of drug release follows Korsmeyer-Peppas model along with non-Fickian diffusion mechanism which leading to the conclusion that a release mechanism of drug followed combination of diffusion and spheres erosion.

TABLE 22: RELEASE KINETICS STUDIES OF THE PREPARED FORMULATIONS

Formulation code	Release model								
	Zero order		First order		Higuchi matrix		Koresmeyer-peppas		
	K	R2	K	R2	K	R2	n	K	R2
T ₁	21.6	0.797	1.923	0.720	-0.313	0.912	0.556	1.388	0.925
T ₂	16.39	0.908	1.991	0.890	-3.945	0.970	0.595	1.326	0.983
T ₃	10.45	0.976	2.062	0.945	-8.966	0.975	0.673	1.233	0.991
T ₄	7.434	0.990	2.118	0.914	-12.25	0.962	0.743	1.171	0.996
T ₅	24.34	0.768	1.897	0.689	2.624	0.903	0.498	1.442	0.914
T ₆	17.19	0.904	1.990	0.885	-3.333	0.971	0.579	1.346	0.981
T ₇	14.53	0.936	2.018	0.985	-6.239	0.983	0.655	1.278	0.990
T ₈	13.06	0.948	2.032	0.991	-7.587	0.984	0.690	1.241	0.991
T ₉	23.20	0.783	1.909	0.704	1.336	0.909	0.526	1.418	0.925
T ₁₀	16.73	0.906	1.992	0.885	-3.771	0.970	0.591	1.334	0.982
T ₁₁	12.50	0.957	2.036	0.974	-7.640	0.982	0.667	1.253	0.993
T ₁₂	11.94	0.959	2.061	0.982	-8.986	0.981	0.712	1.226	0.995

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The microspheres are designed notably to mitigate the dose as well as enhance bioavailability. Microspheres have good biocompatibility with controllable biodegradability. It helps principally to improve patient compliance for chronic disorders microspheres are suitable dosage forms.

The Muco-adhesive microspheres consists of a set of 1-1000nm in diameter. A mucoadhesive microsphere can adhere to any mucosal tissue including eye, nasal cavity, urinary and gastrointestinal tract. The main advantage of a thin mucoadhesive microsphere is it increase bioavailability and efficient absorption.

In the present work, bioadhesive microspheres of Miglitol using Sodium alginate along with Carbopol 934, Carbopol 971, HPMC K4M as copolymers were formulated to deliver Miglitol via oral route.

Details regarding the preparation and evaluation of the formulations have been discussed in the previous chapter. From the study following conclusions could be drawn:-

The results of this investigation indicate that ionic cross linking technique ionotropic gelation method can be successfully employed to fabricate Miglitol microspheres. The technique provides characteristic advantage over conventional microsphere method, which involves an "all- aqueous system, avoids residual solvents in microspheres. Other methods utilize larger volume of organic solvents, which are costly and hazardous because of the possible explosion, air pollution, toxicity and difficult to remove traces of organic solvent completely.

FT-IR spectra of the physical mixture revealed that the drug is compatible with the polymers and copolymers used.

Micromeritic studies revealed that the mean particle size of the prepared microspheres was in the size range of 512-903µm and are suitable for bioadhesive microspheres for oral administration.

Increase in the polymer concentration led to increase in % Yield, % Drug entrapment efficiency, Particle size, % swelling and % Mucoadhesion.

The in-vitro mucoadhesive study demonstrated that microspheres of Miglitol using sodium alginate along with Carbopol934 as copolymer adhered to the mucus to a greater extent than the microspheres of Miglitol using sodium alginate along with Carbopol 971 and HPMC K4M as copolymers.

The invitro drug release decreased with increase in the polymer and copolymer concentration.

Analysis of drug release mechanism showed that the drug release from the formulations followed non-Fickian diffusion and the best fit model was found to be Korsmeyer-Peppas.

Based on the results of evaluation tests formulation coded Ta was concluded as best formulation

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